

‘I’m on the Way Back from the Game’: A Corpus-Assisted Discourse Study Comparing Pronoun Use in the Football Phone-In ‘606’

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Abstract. In this corpus-assisted discourse study, the linguistic environments of pronouns are analysed and compared in calls to the BBC Radio 5 Live football phone-in ‘606’. Phone-ins are ripe for research, as they allow laypeople to debate with professionals to a large audience. This paper examines a 75,000-word corpus of British English football phone-in data to compare pronoun use between callers whose teams won and lost and establishes the themes they construct. Collocation and concordance corpus tools are utilised, allowing for a comparative analysis of 112 transcribed calls, not only comparing usage between pronouns themselves, but also how they are used differently by supporters whose teams won or lost. Collocation results show that the pronouns ‘I’, ‘we’, ‘you’, and ‘they’ are used in constructions that fit into six linguistic and thematic categories. The additional context provided by the concordance analysis shows that these can be simplified into just two purposes: constructing stance and building credibility. There is little difference in how credibility is invoked between the callers whose teams won or lost, but as expected, the losers employ a more negative stance towards their situation. The stance constructions incorporate a variety of pronouns, whilst credibility is primarily built through first person pronouns. I argue that stance is a principal element of calls in programmes where views on a subject are given. Credibility is also paramount, because the callers’ stances can only be taken seriously when they state their credentials to prove they can comment on the topic as an expert.

Keywords: corpus linguistics; football phone-in; collocation; concordance; corpus-assisted discourse studies

1 Introduction

Football phone-ins have been integral to the sport’s media landscape for many years, with the first being broadcast in 1986 (BBC South Yorkshire, 2008), offering callers the chance to air their views to a radio audience in a programme called ‘Praise or Grumble’. Many British stations have since adopted the format, such as the national BBC Radio 5 Live, with 606, the programme featured in this study. It attracts a national audience of callers and listeners, allowing for a representation of a diverse group of people and teams. It is reputable due to the BBC’s status as a broadcaster and its regular schedule means that shows are spread out evenly across the season, giving a profile of fans’ views at different points in time. All phone-ins require a host to interact with the callers, with 606 being presented by former footballers Robbie Savage and Chris Sutton in the 2022/23 season. This period was chosen as the most recently completed season, meaning that data is up to date and an accurate profiling of current trends.

In linguistic research, many studies have explored radio phone-ins, but less attention has been paid to the football subgenre. Previous research helped to shape the research questions of this paper, with those being ‘how does pronoun use differ between supporters whose teams have won and lost?’ and ‘what themes do callers construct?’. To answer these questions, 112 calls from twelve programmes are transcribed, before being separated into two corpora, where callers whose teams lost or won are kept apart. A corpus-assisted discourse analysis framework is used, and collocation and concordance tools highlight language patterns. Collocation statistics are utilised first, raising interesting similarities and

differences that are then explored in more detail with the additional context provided by concordance lines. The analysis focuses on the themes of stance and credibility, through the lens of six collocation categories.

Stance is a central element to the discussion. DuBois (2007, p. 163) defines it as ‘a public act by a social actor, achieved dialogically through overt communicative means, of simultaneously evaluating objects, positioning subjects (self and others), and aligning with other subjects, with respect to any salient dimensions of the sociocultural field’ (as cited in Myers & Lampropoulou, 2012, p. 1208). For a phone-in, these are the views which callers share. Myers and Lampropoulou later write that ‘a crucial aspect of speaker identity is entitlement to answer the specific question one has been asked’ (p. 1216), which forms the definition for credibility, another important theme of this paper. This is concerned with how callers prove that they have the knowledge to speak on a topic, as an expert.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Language and Radio Phone-Ins

Radio phone-ins have frequently been a topic of interest for research. Thornborrow (2001) rationalises this, as they form scenarios where professionals and experts are given the opportunity to interact. Discussion focuses on a given topic, with the role of the host including the assurance that calls provide insight into that topic. Common phone-in themes that have been researched include politics (Hutchby, 1999; Thornborrow, 2001; Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002; Thornborrow & Fitzgerald, 2002; Ellison, 2014; Chichon, 2020), general aspects of life (McCarthy & O’Keeffe, 2003; O’Sullivan, 2005; Kilby & Horowitz, 2013; Roy, 2013; Versteeg & te Molder, 2018), and sport (Xiang, 2003; Ponton, 2011), with Ponton’s research being the only that investigates football programmes. Their intrigue arises from their unique characteristics, such as the gulf in power between host and caller and the public mass audience (Bednarek, 2014, p. 5), hence needing to satisfy what is regarded as a ‘good call’ (O’Sullivan, 2005, p. 732). Interactions are high stakes as a result, with callers being cognisant of the impression they give off and the consequences of how they are perceived (O’Sullivan, 2005, p. 720).

Conversation analysis has often been the methodology used for radio phone-ins (Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002), yet tend to analyse small data sets, unlike the large-scale methodology of corpus analysis. There have been few attempts to collect radio phone-in texts and apply a corpus linguistics framework, despite the many tools offered by the software. McCarthy and O’Keeffe (2003) first built one of these corpora, studying vocatives in a 55,000-word corpus of Irish English. It is clearly distinguished from the present paper, which contains British English and a substantially larger corpus of 75,000 words. The vocatives were deemed to manage turn-taking, topic, and face concerns, which links to pronouns as they both can act as forms of address. Bednarek (2014) then used the 200,000-word Australian corpus of radio talk for a larger research project, where the concept of involvement was studied with the N-Grams tool. She went on to recommend that ‘it might be interesting to look more closely at pronouns’ (p. 14), supporting Roy’s (2013, p. 17) earlier endorsement of pronouns referring to collectivities of people in research, helping to narrow the scope of the present study. More recently, Beeferman et al. (2019) reported on the ambitious project to build a 2.8-billion-word corpus of American radio talk but has been neglected in actual linguistic research since its creation.

Before Bednarek’s recommendation, pronouns have rarely been dealt with explicitly, except Xiang (2003), who found pronouns to collocate with opinion markers to express personal views on American sports radio. Since then, they have received some more focus. In the context of political news radio, Ellison (2014) found a crude binary between the use of pronouns, proposing a contrast between the ‘protagonist we’ and ‘antagonist they’ (p. 98), highlighting an obvious distinction between ingroups

and outgroups. This distinction can be attributed less precisely to second person pronouns, with Jautz (2014) identifying that the pronouns ‘you’ and ‘your’ can involve different people at different junctures of conversation (p. 24). Since this slew of studies, pronouns have again ceased to receive warranted research attention, whilst identity has been a preferred theme.

Outside of the corpus studies, researchers have sought to organise calls, studying the introductory sections where callers are greeted and brought on to speak (Hutchby, 1999; Thornborrow, 2001). These are known as ‘openings’ (Hutchby, 1999) and allow the host to ‘bring the caller into the participatory frame’ (Thornborrow, 2001, p. 122). In these organisation attempts, researchers have noticed that the ‘institutionality’ and power imbalance results in the linguistic tools a caller can use being limited (Hutchby, 1999, p. 57; Thornborrow, 2001, p. 119). Necessary features of the openings are ‘call-relevant identities’ (Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002, p. 586): the information used to describe the caller as they are brought into the conversation. Location is the usual standard, but for football phone-ins the supported team is given instead. Kilby and Horowitz (2013) also stress the importance of this seemingly minor feature. They postulate that listeners already make judgements about the caller at this point, and it is the callers’ goal to provide their ‘expert credentials’ to prove their points are valid. Credibility and identity are heavily interwoven in this genre of communication and described as ‘crucial’ to the whole process by Chichon (2020, p. 5). Being a football fan is deemed a significant identity by society (Gee, 2014, p. 25), so it is therefore interesting to analyse how this identity is managed by radio callers, especially considering that it is a self-ascribed identity.

2.2 Corpus Linguistics

Corpus linguistics (CL) is the large-scale study of language aided by computer technologies (Partington et al., 2013). The modern corpus tools allow for a fast and reliable analysis of large bodies of texts, with this collection of texts being known as corpora (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 2). In some form, corpus linguistics has existed long before computers revolutionised the process, but the neo-Firthian school and its main proponent John Sinclair helped to establish the methodology in use today. The concepts of collocation and discourse are central to this (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 122). The studies that have been since been conducted examine an incredible range of topics, which shows how the methodology can be applicable to almost any research question. The emergence of the internet has allowed for corpora and corpus tools to be shared, helping to create this productive research community (Crosthwaite et al., 2023, p. 365). McEnery and Hardie distinguish between the established ideas of ‘corpus-based’ and ‘corpus-driven’ studies, with corpus-driven following the neo-Firthian methodology of a ‘bottom up’ study, whilst corpus-based is defined as ‘top down’. Put simply, the researcher has no preconceived notions about what they might find in corpus-driven research, on the contrary, they may be aiming for a more targeted analysis if it is corpus-based (2012, pp. 241-242). Partington builds on the traditional ideas by offering ‘corpus-assisted discourse studies’ (CADS), which is defined as a CL subset that uses computerised corpora to study language ‘as communicative discourse’ (2013, p. 10). Crosthwaite et al. (2023) map out the trends in CL research over the past 20 years, finding CADS research to rank highly alongside work studying social media, politics, and news discourse. The bibliometric data reveals the long-lasting impact of the influential researchers and the cumulative effect they have had on emerging researchers who cite their early works (p. 366).

Concordance analysis is widely regarded as a key component of CL research (Gillings & Mautner, 2023, p. 1). A concordance tool can provide a ‘display of every instance of a specified word or other search term in a corpus’ (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 241), also giving the context on either side of the search term. These can be investigated to find any thematic co-selections and how they create meaning (Cheng, 2011, p. 8) and these patterns can be syntactic, semantic, or a combination of both (Gillings &

Mautner, 2023, p. 1). To ensure that these conclusions are reliable, researchers must decide whether to alter their texts, as interpreting the contextual information of concordances can prove challenging. Gillings and Mautner recommend that the researcher flags these decisions to the reader (2023, p. 7).

Collocation tools can also prove to be beneficial in CL research, which is defined as a ‘co-occurrence relationship between two words’ (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 240). The tools can provide data for how frequently words appear near each other and when they are found, they are a result of a single choice, rather than two (Cheng, 2011, p. 77). This suggests that speakers can be predisposed to use certain words in a particular linguistic context, and this can prove interesting to compare across corpora exactly how context-specific it can be.

2.3 Language and Community

A key focus for this research is the idea of language and community. Football fandom is itself a form of community, which exists on multiple levels. How callers manage their identity with regards to their communities is a point of interest, which will be explored linguistically through the lens of pronouns.

Mercer (2007) describes how, amongst other offerings, communities give their members a discourse and a collective identity (p. 108). He adds to Lave and Wenger’s theory of ‘communities of practice’, which are defined as ‘groups which are united by common purposes and who engage in joint activity’ (p. 116), so football fandom is certainly applicable to this idea. Viggiano (2021) applies this model within a corpus analysis, noting that the concept has been adapted to include virtual communities (pp. 59-60). The activities members partake in, and the shared knowledge gained over time, help to contextualise what brings the community together. Mercer posits that there are relations within groups, as new members are ‘trained’ by ‘experts’ (p. 116) and exposure to the narratives of experts helps the new members to ‘speak the discourse’ (p. 117). On the other hand, he reinforces how it is difficult for members to share thoughts which could be deemed unconventional in the discourse (p. 115). Therefore, callers need to manage this carefully if they intend to do so, so they could employ techniques such as vagueness, where the message is implied but able to be defended against if questioned.

Older work also highlights the relevance of language as a means of constructing identity and community. Fairclough (1989) makes a similar identification by mentioning the role of ‘discourse as a social practice’, where ‘the language activity which goes on in social contexts... is *part* of those processes and practices’ (p. 23). This is especially true for a radio phone-in, as language is virtually the only tool for callers to use when communicating through this medium. An interesting theory presented by Fairclough is that of ‘member resources (MR)’ (p. 11), which are socially determined prototypes for typical narrative structures and expected sequences of events. Mercer (2007) identifies another facet of a community being a ‘history’ (p. 108), so the evolution of discourse over time contributes to the typical language that might be used, helping to shape MR. Knowledge of these MR help to give credibility to speakers and position themselves as experts. Fairclough refers to how underlying conventions determine the organisation of discourse (p. 28). Speakers who break these conventions distinguish themselves from the rest of their community and are at risk of being dismissed or ridiculed. The conventions also determine how power is constrained (p. 47) and create power imbalances between established experts and new members.

Plenty of research has analysed the use of pronouns as a means of constructing community. Recently, Hadikin (2020) conducted a corpus analysis of the string ‘we are’ in an online community forum and found writers were ‘primed to use certain strings’ (p. 75). Pavlidou (2014) describes how self-attribution to different groups can be invoked by the pronoun ‘we’, and its use determines those people as a group (p. 7). These can extend over ‘different domains’ (p. 5), so the contextual information is needed to deduce who qualifies and who does not (p. 8).

Other pronouns have proved to be matters of interest, such as in Myers and Lampropoulou’s paper concerning the impersonal ‘you’ (2012). They argue that it is a marker of stance, as well as categorising speakers into groups (p. 1211), similarly to the ‘we’ function. It invokes an idea of shared perception (p. 1212), because the implication is that someone without the experiences of the speaker could expect to see something similar. A useful conclusion is that entitlement to answer a question is key to a speaker’s identity (p. 1216), so this provides another usage where the ultimate function is to build credibility. This could be prevalent in radio phone-ins, as callers need to prove this entitlement by showing how they are qualified to contribute to the programme.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Selection

Many radio calls were needed to address the research questions and form a sizable corpus of authentic spoken texts. Several radio phone-ins exist in the UK, but the BBC Radio 5 Live programme ‘606’ was chosen due to its reputable status and regular schedule of two programmes on Saturday and Sunday each weekend of the season. As the most recently completed season, the 2022/23 English Premier League (EPL) was chosen to ensure analysis of current language trends on the show. Initially, it was intended to use BBC Sounds as the source of past programmes, but these were deleted at the beginning of the new season in August 2023. Box of Broadcasts (Learning on Screen, 2023) was used instead to reliably collect data.

Based on a small sample to test the forthcoming transcription process, I calculated that I would be able to transcribe calls from 12 programmes in the allocated timeframe. I split these into six Saturday and six Sunday programmes, to ensure as many teams as possible were represented in the corpus. A random number generator was used to generate numbers between six and 38 that aligned with the corresponding rounds in the season. The first five rounds were discounted due to the calls being more prospective, whereas I wanted to focus on callers’ reactions to matches. Three programmes were randomly chosen, but discarded as they did not maximise the number of potential calls in the corpus. For two of these, cup matches dominated the programmes, which were discarded due to the different factors at play in these competitions. Table 1.1 shows the programmes that were chosen and their inclusion.

Table 1.1: *Programme inclusion*

Round	Sat. Date	Sun. Date	Inclusion in Final Corpus	Reason If Discarded
11	15 th October 2022	16 th October 2022	Yes	
13	22 nd October 2022	23 rd October 2022	Yes	
16	12 th November 2022	13 th November 2022	Yes	
20	14 th January 2023	15 th January 2023	Yes	
25	25 th February 2023	26 th February 2023	No	Cup matches taking place
26	4 th March 2023	5 th March 2023	Yes	
28	18 th March 2023	19 th March 2023	No	Cup matches taking place
31	15 th April 2023	16 th April 2023	Yes	
32	22 nd April 2023	23 rd April 2023	No	One programme this weekend

Once these were identified, I began the transcription process.

3.1.1 First Transcription Stage

After the programmes were requested and available for listening, I noted the caller’s team, result, time stamp, and first name for identification, as well as any potential variable that could mean that call would need to be discarded. Once completed, the criteria for inclusion were decided. The calls were transcribed with several alterations for a thorough corpus analysis, hence they stray from Hammersley’s (2010) idea of ‘strict transcriptions’ (p. 559), so the rationale for each decision will be discussed in turn.

There was an uneven number of callers in the winner’s calls (WC) and loser’s calls (LC), with 70 winner calls compared to 55 loser calls. Three teams were overrepresented, so each was capped at seven calls, therefore the conclusions are representative of all teams, rather than the most popular ones. After balancing, 13 calls were discarded, resulting in a final WC of 57 calls. The study focuses on the EPL only, so fifteen Scottish and lower league English calls were discarded, because they featured too infrequently to judge if fans of these competitions differed in their language use when calling. The largest reason for discarding calls was due to the result being a draw. They are perceived as an in-between outcome, with elements of victory and defeat. Supporters rarely call up afterwards, with them accounting for just over 10% of the total calls, so they were not afforded their own category. The following table shows a breakdown of the reasons some calls were not included.

Table 1.2: *Breakdown of discarded calls*

Reason	No.	% of Discarded Calls	% of All Calls (166)
Draw	17	31.48%	10.24%
Team Outside of EPL	15	27.78%	9.04%
Corpus Balancing	13	24.07%	7.83%
Team Did Not Play	3	5.56%	1.81%
Debate with Previous Caller	2	3.70%	1.20%
Talking About Different Team	2	3.70%	1.20%
Ethical Concerns	1	1.85%	0.60%
Unfinished Game	1	1.85%	0.60%
Total	54		32.53%

3.1.2 Second Transcription Stage

This stage comprises the automatic transcription of the calls. The duration is determined from the presenters' introductory greeting until they thank the caller for participating. If they are instead cut off without a farewell, the transcription ends with the caller’s final utterance. Interruptions for the news, interviews, or live sport updates are removed, and the transcription continues when the caller is reintroduced. The audio quality of the programme was poor, resulting in difficulty picking up the sound with ordinary speakers. To mitigate this, the calls were played through a Bluetooth speaker and transcribed automatically, using the Otter.ai software (2018).

3.1.3 Third Transcription Stage

The software is not always accurate, so the aim of this stage was to ensure that the transcriptions are an exact replication of what is said by the callers and presenters. I played the audio and paused to make corrections, then listened once more to ensure complete accuracy.

3.1.4 Fourth Transcription Stage

The final stage involved making the final edits before inputting them into a concordancer. This process was intended to make the corpus a better imitation of written language, so the concordance and collocation patterns could be more comparable and consistent between the corpora, so stuttering, repairs, and self-corrections were removed to create more coherent language. Non-standard verb forms were also changed to ensure comparability in the collocation analysis. Repetition for effect, however, was left unchanged. Albeit in a non-academic source, Williams (2018) notes that this is a feature of the English football lexicon, using the example ‘top, top player’ (p. 88). Fillers are a common feature across the transcriptions and, again, as to not disturb the concordance patterns, they are removed when disrupting the flow of speech, but are kept when occurring between clauses to give an idea of a speaker’s potential hesitancy. The final alteration was to retrospectively add subject pronouns that were deleted. As this study analyses pronouns, they are easier to investigate using corpus methods when they are physically present in the texts, instead of being implied.

The texts were converted to individual plain text files to be compatible with the concordance software ‘AntConc’ (Anthony, 2014). The texts were initially separated into two folders, with the winners’ and losers’ calls kept apart for similarities and differences to be found. From this, another two folders were created, but with the presenters’ dialogue removed. As the focus is concerned with supporter discourse, these two corpora will be primarily used, with the full corpora only being used to provide context where it is otherwise not clear. The caller utterances are tagged with a ‘C:’ before they speak.

Table 1.3: Subcorpora word counts

Corpus	Word Count
Winners Corpus (WC)	37236
Losers Corpus (LC)	36887
Winners Corpus Callers Only (WCCO)	23584
Losers Corpus Callers Only (LCCO)	24674

Ethics were a great consideration during this process and any identifiable information given by the callers was deleted from the corpus. Any information deemed overly specific was removed, whilst making minimal disruption to the texts. My institution’s ethical procedures were followed, and an ethics form was submitted and signed without issue.

The following table shows a small section of a larger breakdown of the callers in the corpus. The entire table in Appendix 1 shows the information of each caller that determined inclusion.

Table 1.4: Sample of participants breakdown

Caller Name	Supported Team	Team Result	Date of Programme	Corpus Inclusion	Discard Reason
Nick	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Joe	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	

Glyn	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Ollie	Bournemouth	Drew	15 th October	No	Draw
Gareth	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Luke	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Derek	Celtic	Won	15 th October	No	Scottish team
Jo	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Matthew	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Bart	Manchester City	Did not play	15 th October	No	Did not play

Including a diverse range of teams allows for a comprehensive profile of football supporters throughout England. Due to the fanbase sizes, some teams will form a larger part of the corpus. An advantage of the large corpus is that virtually all the teams in the league were represented at least once, but due to their results appeared more in one compared to the other. The only team that did not appear was Southampton. This was not remedied to avoid cherry picking data and it would not have been time effective to find a Southampton caller in another programme.

Table 1.5: *Representation of teams in subcorpora*

Team	No. of calls in WC Before Balancing	No. of Calls in WC	No. of Calls in LC
Arsenal	12	7	0
Aston Villa	4	4	2
Bournemouth	1	1	0
Brentford	1	1	0
Brighton	2	2	3
Chelsea	6	6	5
Crystal Palace	1	1	3
Everton	2	2	7
Fulham	0	0	1
Leeds	0	0	2
Leicester	1	1	4
Liverpool	13	7	4
Manchester City	6	6	4
Manchester United	9	7	2
Newcastle	3	3	2
Nottingham Forest	2	2	2
Southampton	0	0	0
Tottenham	5	5	8
West Ham	0	0	4
Wolves	2	2	2
Total	70	57	55

3.2 Analytical Approach

Corpus analysis is the primary analytical tool that will be utilised in this analysis. More specifically, a CADS framework is applied to investigate the discourse of football phone-ins. The analysis forms a hybrid between quantitative and qualitative methods, with the preconception of a focus on pronouns allowing for a more refined study, but what is found in the corpus itself will be used in whatever form it takes to answer the research questions. What is considered an interesting finding is subjective to the researcher, so themes of credibility and stance will be prioritised as they link directly to the outlined research questions.

3.2.1 Concordance

The ability to analyse ‘key words in context’ is a feature of AntConc that will be used. A certain word or phrase can be searched in the concordancer and a given number of words context on both sides, providing an ordered presentation for the linguistic environment the search term can be found in. In this analysis, pronouns will be the input to find concordance patterns on both sides. This allows for patterns to be found by making connections between the words appearing around the search term.

3.2.2 Collocation

The collocation tool enables more focused analysis, as it provides the most frequent words that appear directly alongside others. For this analysis, pronouns will again form the input into this tool, with collocation patterns on either side. More specifically, the right side will likely provide more interesting patterns. Due to the *Subject-Verb-Object* sentence structure in English, subject pronouns will often begin sentences, so the preceding word will be separate and unrelated. By this definition, verbs will be expected to occur alongside subject pronouns, so they will be analysed to see what they achieve in interaction. This is a useful starting point for research, as it gives an idea of the kinds of terms that are worth analysing using the more precise tools.

4 Analysis

The collocation results were able to be separated into six categories, based on their word class and thematic meaning. These are shown in tables throughout this analysis, with the numbers corresponding to their ranking according to AntConc’s likelihood measure. The totals are not consistent for each pronoun, so Table 2 shows the total number of collocates for each. The numbers were capped at 30, as to not overwhelm the reader with data.

Table 2: *Collocation totals*

Corpus	I	We	You	They
WCCO	30	23	17	11
LCCO	30	23	10	15

4.1 Constructing Stance

4.1.1 Opinion Markers

Table 3.1: *Winners Corpus opinion markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
agree	15			
feel	18			
knew	26			
know	20		1	
look			3	
love	10			
mean	3			
need		20		
needed		23		
reckon	28			
think	1		13	
thought	7			
wanted	12			

Table 3.2: *Losers Corpus opinion markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
agree	16			
believe	12			
expected	29			
feel	20			
hate	22			
hope	26			
know	15		1	
look			8	
love	25			
mean	3			
need		4		
seemed				11
suppose	18			
think	1			
thought	7			

The primary manner of realising stance is through opinion markers. The tables show slight variation in the markers used, with those in bold indicating they collocate in both corpora. Many of the corpus-specific collocates are different word forms or synonyms for more common terms. The most interesting to note are the LC rankings of the very negative ‘hate’ and the slightly sceptical ‘suppose’. These collocates show a preference for callers talking about their thoughts and emotions to the hosts and listeners. This phenomenon tends to be realised in the ‘I’ environment, which is understandable as the caller cannot speak on behalf of those who agree or disagree; they cannot say what is going on in *their* heads, so instead bring others into the conversation in other collocation categories. The verb ‘know’ ranks highest out of all second person ‘you’ collocations, with ‘look’ also featuring in the list. A vast number of callers will frequently use ‘you know’ as a filler between clauses, with the goal of enticing support from the hosts. If the hosts respond with agreement, this greatly benefits the callers, who could

be seen as putting their point across successfully. The verb ‘need’ only collocates with the first-person plural pronoun ‘we’, the only feature for both terms. Furthermore, ‘they’ only collocates with ‘seemed’ in the LC.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 CarlASTWon51C.txt	mention today, I heard the Tottenham fan going on about his owner and whatever and	I think it	s time that people celebrated the Villa owners, and also Chris Purslow,
2 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	time last year. They had top four in their hands and then they bottled it.	I think it	s the same thing. I think it's all well and good
3 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	in their hands and then they bottled it. I think it's the same thing.	I think it	s all well and good to have a blip but at this
4 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	in every competition last year until the last minute. There was a World Cup and	I think it	s a wee bit of burnout. I think they were meant to
5 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	I think they were meant to have a few players playing in the World Cup.	I think it	s a wee bit of burnout, but the right man's there.
6 MoCHEWon42C.txt	You know, what he did for the club in that year was just amazing, but	I think it	s pointless sacking Potter now when I think it's more of
7 MoCHEWon42C.txt	that year was just amazing, but I think it's pointless sacking Potter now when	I think it	s more of a backwards step. I think if we can get
8 MoCHEWon42C.txt	I think with the new signings as well and the interviews that he's had	I think it	s fair to say that he should be sacked. I don't
9 PatrickARSWon37C.txt	come back from injury. So we're vulnerable. We're ahead, but we're vulnerable,	I think it	s okay to say that, yeah.
10 PhilARSWon35C.txt	again. And United for me, they're third or fourth or whatever they are, but	I think it	s between us and United.
11 ShazARSWon34C.txt	Hi, Robbie. Hi, Chris. Yeah,	I think it	s a great performance. Every week I think maybe we're not
12 ShazARSWon34C.txt	but then after about four or five weeks into the season, I start believing and	I think it	s about time all the Arsenal fans start believing now and I
13 YayaARSWon44C.txt	twenty six games. So it's an amazing time to be an Arsenal fan. And	I think it	s incredible to see the progress within the last three years since
14 YayaARSWon44C.txt	s incredible to see the progress within the last three years since Arteta came and	I think it	s a lesson for all the clubs to really believe in the
15 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	the league cup. Good luck to him. We beat United seven nil today. Chris, yeah,	I think it	has been burnout. I mean, we played every game last year right
16 DamonASTWon26C.txt	have worked something out, personally. I was never one to get on his back and	I think it	is that sort of balance between "is it the manager, is it
17 MarkBREWon22C.txt	Brentford side is gonna turn up, that's the trouble, but I tell you what	I think it	is. Last season we lost one nil at home and two nil
18 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	you ask what's Wolves' identity now, I'm not sure I could answer that.	I think it	just looks a bit messy at times and I think Nuno would
19 NickTOTWon1C.txt	m just saying I saw it and I don't think it was a penalty.	I think it	was a bit of a coming together. I think the VAR shouldn't
20 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	old son and we've been bickering about it all week, gents, to be honest.	I think it	would be a good move to get him back. I think people
21 DaveASTWon17C.txt	can be quite fickle, as you know. Yeah it's a massive call, especially considering	I think it	s his first actual Premier League game in charge of a club.
22 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	difference there. I don't think after the loss, well it's a draw but	I think it	s a loss, I think he shouldn't have said it straight
23 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	today, great performance by Everton today. Calvert-Lewin especially coming back made a big difference.	I think it	was a fantastic goal. We sit in the paddock, which is near

Figure 1.1: *Winners corpus 'I think it' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 AlexASTLost9C.txt	everything he's got and I'm afraid it was awful. It was absolutely diabolical.	I think it	s the lack of coaching and that's why the manager has
2 BenLEELost13C.txt	Gnonto now feel, you know, he's not played, a full Italian international. Helpful? Do	I think it	s helpful? I don't think it's hurtful. I don't
3 BrianLEILost43C.txt	Southampton didn't have to play until the following night. Yeah, not because of football,	I think it	s just because of the rules now. That stupid thing, I mean,
4 DuncanCRYLost10C.txt	now after, last week, we just scraped by Wolves. I just want Vieira gone now.	I think it	s just an absolute shambles. Vieira gone. Absolutely. Absolutely, I think the
5 JamesEVELost28C.txt	comes out today of all days when the fans are having a sit in protest,	I think it	s convenient that all of a sudden, all this comes out, and
6 JamieCHELost19C.txt	he is now and I think he needs the time he needs at Chelsea and	I think it	s a rebuild for us and if we give him the time
7 JamieMUNLost44C.txt	on the linesman, that's really disappointing and I think I agree with you, Chris.	I think it	s a really bad day. I think United will be fine and,
8 KevinWOLLost15C.txt	was being told what players he's got to bring in or what have you.	I think it	s still the same now, the signings they've made. No, I
9 LouisTOTLost35C.txt	pains me to say, but I think this is partly down to Conte, but equally	I think it	s a much bigger issue at Tottenham than that. I think this
10 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	like to think that I'm not, like children, get influenced by bad role models.	I think it	s completely correct. I agree with you. I tell the boys in
11 TazTOTLost34C.txt	know, pressure is on. Lloris, it's time to go, sorry. You retired from France,	I think it	s time to go from Spurs as well. Thank you very much.
12 LeeCHELost51C.txt	percentages. A percentagician. I don't want to say it again. Maybe forty nine percent.	I think it	could be. What did you say? Yeah, a percentagician. No, that's
13 NickTOTLost50C.txt	can change the formation, you can try changing something, but he just never did. And	I think it	got to the stage where he had so much going on in
14 DeanMCILost5C.txt	weren't as direct as we were, sort of slowing it down quite a lot.	I think it	is the fear of in behind because we do have the high
15 MichaelEVELost47C.txt	Evening, guys. I think I've been at a historic game today in that	I think it	will be the last ever three o'clock kickoff on a Saturday
16 LeeCHELost51C.txt	at me. Right, look at the table. We're closer to relegation than the top.	I think it	s nine points now. If they win their game in hand. And
17 PatrickCRYLost37C.txt	you know, there needs to be a change at the Palace. Yeah. I think so.	I think it	s time. Well, what's he done? What's he done this
18 PennyNEWLost46C.txt	Brentford are and I would love to see someone like Brentford really, really do well.	I think it	s the latter of those, Robbie. I really do. I think Manchester

Figure 1.2: *Losers Corpus 'I think it' concordance.*

The principal, most common stance construction is shown by concordance lines for ‘I think’. Due to its vast frequency in the corpus, the search term is more refined to pinpoint a more specific pattern, which can be gleaned from the concordance for ‘I think it’. As mentioned, this is an integral construction that callers can employ to convey their opinion and would often provide a brief synopsis of the reason they called into the programme. Thornborrow (2001, p. 134) observed that hosts can judge whether a caller has supplied a sufficient answer, so their role is to prevent a caller from going on irrelevant ramblings.

To clarify their point, callers deploy an ‘I think’ structure that grants them the ability to summarise the argument they wanted to make. It is a mutual benefit, because a direct and to-the-point call will be easier to interpret and support, but also helps the hosts, who are not needed to intervene in the organisation of the call and can manoeuvre between callers more easily. The actual construction itself tends to show a polarising attitude and as could be expected, the winners tend to be more positive, exemplified by lines 11, 13, and 23, and the losers are very negative in 4, 7, and 9. The winners themselves are a little more measured, whereas the emotion of defeat can result in an extreme call. When assessing the actual context of when this construction is used, it becomes clear that it mostly expresses the opinion on the recent match or the state of the team’s season. The caller can impart information that the listener might not know or have realised, helping, amongst a fandom, to share thoughts between the group. In a method of callers negotiating the power imbalance between themselves and the expert hosts, they make judgements on what is acceptable to say. They position themselves equally as experts by being able to critically form an opinion on the discussion at hand. It could also be a way of carefully managing a more controversial opinion, such as WC 8 and 9. Versteeg and te Molder (2018, p. 719) acknowledge that radio phone-ins deviate from face-to-face conversation, as hosts actively engage in confrontation, so callers need to manage alternative opinions to defend against this disputation.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	and then obviously we did spend in the January that he was there, but then	you look	at the back five. We've got our back five there, only four
2 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	back five there. We bought obviously Bruno Guimaraes in, as well, and Chris Wood. Then	you look	at the injuries, also, that Newcastle have suffered. No Saint-Maximin, Guimaraes has
3 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	ve conceded the least goals. So, let me put this across to you then. If	you look	at the Newcastle squad, and you look at Arsenal, Liverpool, Manchester City and
4 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	I liked him a lot, but he tends to go on the right side and	you look	at the ones alongside him, Stones right side, Kyle Walker right side. I
5 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	to be patient, you want to, but then there's another side of it where	you look	at the evidence with your eyes and what you see and you're
6 MatthewCHEWon40C.txt	just heartbreaking to see the way they are, the way they're playing. And when	you look	at the likes of Mason Mount, we're probably going to lose Mason
7 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	ten, I wouldn't say any higher than that for this season. I think if	you look	at the top six, it's going to be very difficult for anyone
8 MoCHEWon42C.txt	and I don't think he deserves to be sacked after just a tough season.	You look	at the injuries that we've had this season. I mean, some of
9 JaydenNEWWon18C.txt	manage those big personalities when you've got big players in the teams, but when	you look	at when Eddie Howe came in obviously took over Steve Bruce, Newcastle at
10 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	opinions on this. When they talk about a left sided centre back. Exactly, I mean,	you look	at when Southgate took over England, he said 'I'll consider players playing
11 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	me put this across to you then. If you look at the Newcastle squad, and	you look	at Arsenal, Liverpool, Manchester City and even Tottenham we'll include, and Liverpool
12 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	the Premier League, which I would never have said at the start of season. When	you look	at it really, obviously we've played a game more, so net, probably
13 PeterMUNWon33C.txt	because by the rules of the law, he wasn't interfering with play and if	you look	at ref's guide, the ref's guide said there's actually a
14 ShaunLNVon10C.txt	score the goals, he's putting them on a plate for players all the time.	You look	at Salah, his assists and his goals are always near the top. Now
15 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	blessed with left sided defenders, Robbie and Chris, they're not. So, I mean, when	you look	at that squad now, Conor Coady, I liked him a lot, but he
16 BenLNVon47C.txt	ve got Gakpo, we've got Nunez, we've got young lads. But then if	you look	at those who are going to be leaving, Bobby Firmino, that's a
17 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	think the whole world, including him, in his head was all over the shop. If	you look	back before that, we were super organised, right, we had it, we had
18 AaronMUNWon29C.txt	I'm very well, Chris, how are you doing? Robbie, how are	you? Look,	I know Chris said a seven, me personally I would give him a

Figure 1.3: *Winners Corpus* ‘you look’ concordance.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 BrianLEILost43C.txt	They are rubbish. Well, I mean, in the Premiership we have, they're shocking. If	you look	at it, Iheanacho should have had four. No, they didn't play us.
2 DuncanCRYLost10C.txt	the best teams in South London, aren't we? I think so. I mean, when	you look	at it, we've been in the League for long enough now. I
3 BernardWHULost32C.txt	that immensely. I don't think he's used Paqueta in his best position. Really,	you look	at the way he played for Brazil in the World Cup and I
4 LindonEVELost31C.txt	saying is, right, there's players out there, that will come to Everton, because if	you look	at the top teams, right, that are in the top half of the
5 JimTOTLost33C.txt	But my point for today, ringing up, Chris, was, I believe, truthfully, that you know,	you look	at Arteta at Arsenal. He's got Arsenal blood flowing through his veins.
6 TonyMCIlost18C.txt	last five. I take your point, I know what you're saying. Phil Foden, if	you look	at him, he's constantly looking to pass the ball to Erling Haaland.
7 ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	top of League One now, looking like they might get into the Championship and then	you look	at Levy building Mario Kart courses underneath the stadium and all the rest

Figure 1.4: *Losers corpus* ‘you look’ concordance.

Diverting focus to second person pronouns, the frequent collocation of a ‘you look’ structure is worth attention. It becomes immediately apparent that the referent is vague, a function researched extensively by Myers and Lampropoulou (2012). They note that the person or people being addressed in interaction are the usual referent when ‘you’ is used, but another use they define as ‘a kind of impersonal reference

that does not pick out any particular person, but is the equivalent of someone, anyone, or one' (p. 1206). In the present corpora, this construction conveys an opinion that the caller deems to be obvious and assumes that the hosts and listeners would agree, such as WC 7, 13, and 17. The meaning of the verb 'look' is not meant literally; the caller does not want the listener to see something but is instead concerned with noticing a certain pattern. By deploying an imperative or conditional structure, as in the above cases with 'if' featuring immediately before the search term, the caller outlines a method that anyone would be able to follow and come to the same conclusion. This phenomenon is mirrored in Myers and Lampropoulou (2012, p. 1210), who suggest that the speakers recategorise themselves into a more general set of people to give the impression that many other people would relay the same message if they were in the same scenario. Alternatively, someone without these experiences could experience it for the first time and expect to see what the interlocutor has described. The caller positions themselves as an expert by being able to comment on an experience as shared, which itself bolsters the argument by invoking the stance of other people. They are presenting themselves as able to accurately interpret the matters at hand and transfer that information to others. It tends to be more common in the WC, with both corpora employing positive and negative stances. As before, the LC is a little more polarising, with humour used to mock players and owners. This is not present in the WC, so shows how the losers call the programme as a way of dealing with the negative emotions associated with a poor result.

4.1.2 Auxiliary Verbs

Table 4.1: *Winners Corpus auxiliary verbs*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	11	17		6
did		14		
didn't	25	13		10
do	22			
don't	4		11	
had		4		
'm/'re	2	1	2	1
've	5	2	5	2
was/were	8	3	17	3
wasn't/weren't				5

Table 4.2: *Losers Corpus auxiliary verbs*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	10			4
did				
didn't		15		13
don't	4	18	9	
had		9		
have		20		
haven't		7		12
'm/'re	2	2	2	1

've	6	1	3	2
was/were	13	3		3
wasn't/weren't				7

The grammatical function of auxiliary verbs means that there is little variation between the corpora. It is natural for them to provide common collocations due to their high frequency and necessity in some tense constructions. This collocation category has a hybrid function, invoking both stance *and* credibility. The credibility element will be explored in Section 4.2. The different word forms are paired, because they have the exact same meanings, and the difference is only grammatical. The only significant difference is shown by the increased chance of 'haven't' collocating in the LC, ranking highly in the 'we' environment. It might have been expected to see a comparative increase in negated auxiliary verbs in the LC, but this example is the only one that shows an indication of this being the case. When comparing between pronouns, the 'I' environment shows a higher quantity of collocations in the WC, but a lower quantity of 'we' collocations. Overall, contracted forms are preferred, hinting at a potentially informality in the genre. This opposes the patterns identified by Hadikin (2020), who found a high level of formality to show expertise and education. This is also a desired intention of radio callers but is realised in different ways.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	one of our famous runs that we've done in the last few years. And	we're going	to win the Premier League and then in the FA Cup Manchester
2 ShazARSWon41C.txt	for you as well. Do you think where Arsenal were last season and considering when	we're going	to win, I'm not going to say if because I think
3 YayaARSWon44C.txt	of atmosphere, I think is making a difference to Arsenal. I'm not gonna say	we're going	to win the league. We obviously should, from where we are now.
4 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	your league cup win. So what, you won a league cup. My point is that	we're going	nowhere. I'm a Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan
5 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	done over the last few years, Bobby's been in the middle of it all.	We're going	nowhere. We're here forever, Robbie, We're never going to stop.
6 DamonASTWon26C.txt	been awful at the start of the season. But for the last couple of weeks,	we're going	into the break happy, so up the Villa. Do I think we'
7 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	re going nowhere. I'm a Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan from 1973.	We're going	nowhere and, okay, we beat United seven nil today but I expected
8 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	He should be happy. But they got beat seven nil today, by the mighty reds,	we're going	nowhere, right, and I was saying to a guy the other day.
9 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	We're going nowhere. We're here forever, Robbie, We're never going to stop.	We're going	nowhere. Of course. You think a manager that's won a few
10 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	easy because Arsenal are bottling it, they're bottling it right now. And I think	we're going	on a run, one of our famous runs that we've done
11 YayaARSWon44C.txt	it really is when you have a clear vision, when you have a clear synergy	we're gonna	achieve so it's incredible. I'm really over the moon. No.
12 BenLIVWon47C.txt	sat on the edge of our seats thinking "oh they're gonna lose the ball,	we're gonna	do this", you know, I think Konate, going back into that back
13 EmmaNFWon32C.txt	He got us promoted last year, he took us to Wembley. I don't think	we're gonna	forget that. What, jealousy that we have stayed up? How many years
14 JoshARSWon39C.txt	game. At two nil down, yeah, of course you would because you were thinking "right	we're gonna	lose this, our lead is only going to be two points". But
15 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	week saved, we can maybe go and get the likes of Ivan Toney and now	we're gonna	pay more than we would have at the start of the season.
16 JoeWOLWon2C.txt	nineteen, twenty year old injury prone player from Colombia, so I don't know who	we're gonna	play. I don't want to play boring, round the back, defensive
17 ShazARSWon41C.txt	confirms what I knew a couple of months ago that this season is ours and	we're gonna	win the title and more and more people are starting to believe.

Figure 2.1: *Winners Corpus 'we're go*' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 DannyFULLost24.txt	re overachieving. There's going to be a point for the season, coming up, where	we're going	to drop points, hundred percent. It's going to come up. At
2 EmmaCHELost54C.txt	I've seen us win the league and I've got to be happy that	we're going	to be a mid table team. I'm going on Tuesday against
3 GarethEVElost2C.txt	and Pickford knew that. Kane's done nothing wrong. I mean I'm Welsh, so	we're going	to be playing Harry Kane in the World Cup and I'd
4 JamesEVElost28C.txt	come out in midweek and back him one hundred percent, then that says to me,	we're going	to stick with him. Now the fans have also got to stick
5 JamieCHELost19C.txt	every faith in Graham Potter. I think he just needs that time and I think	we're going	to do well. I think we can do well.
6 NickTOTLost50C.txt	I ain't going anywhere near that, Jesus Christ'. So I don't know who	we're going	to end up with. I guarantee we'll end up with either
7 PennyNEWLost46C.txt	degree are pretty much a well established team and we all pretty much know what	we're going	to get. With those others it's a surprise, isn't it?
8 SimonWHULost41C.txt	of us had to stay up there because we couldn't get a train back.	We're going	to Cyprus next week. I didn't go today because I'm
9 MarkLEILost30C.txt	give him a lot of money. But if they don't give him that money,	we're going	down or, we're like James the Everton fan was saying, we'
10 ChrisLIVLost26C.txt	can pull them back up. He hasn't done it in five months, has he?	We're going	down. We're eighth. You know, teams like Villa, who lost to
11 JamieMUNLost44C.txt	Liverpool are playing for nothing. I know they've had their cup final today, but	we're going	in different directions, I think. Liverpool, fair play to them, but we
12 ChrisLIVLost26C.txt	Got Wolves next week, replay, then we've got Chelsea. I can't really see	we're gonna	get anything out of that. So we've had five months, this
13 PatLIVLost29C.txt	team driving forward. And it was almost like 'come on lads, do your best but	we're gonna	get nothing out of this game today'. Teams don't train to
14 PatLIVLost29C.txt	top four is a bitter pill, really. Fourth, yes, I mean, I don't think	we're gonna	get any higher than fourth and we'd be lucky to do
15 MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	I mean, come on. Palace is always gonna be a mid table team. You know,	we're gonna	be there. If we can stay up, for me, that's a
16 MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	there. If we can stay up, for me, that's a bonus and anyone thinks	we're gonna	go into Europe or do anything better, I mean, they need to
17 GordonNEWLost49C.txt	game at St. James' on Sunday. It's not far from Izmir. That's where	we're going.	I think so, yes. I'll catch you when I come back,

Figure 2.2: Losers Corpus 'we're go*' concordance.

The environment of 'we're going' and the contracted 'we're gonna' show some of the clearest contrasts between winning and losing. By employing this structure, they are referring to something that the caller predicts will happen in the near future. The callers' goals are to remind people that their team is at their peak and will be staying there for the foreseeable future. In the WC, this construction is usually concerned with a prediction of success, where the team wins an individual game or a piece of silverware, such as in 1, 3, and 11. By using the first-person plural pronoun, the supporters identify their own role in propelling their team to success. They see it as a reward for their loyal support and will position themselves alongside the team to celebrate their achievements. This helps to galvanise the fanbase because they feel part of the community. In the LC, a sense of pessimism prevails in 1, 9, 10, and 14, with the callers expecting a worst-case scenario, even mentioning relegation in some calls. The recency bias of these callers seeing their team lose results in a difficulty to compartmentalise, as it is not so simple to stay positive after defeat.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 BenCRYWon50C.txt	at the moment. Why wouldn't you be? The Gallagher hole was huge. You know,	you don't	know how big a hole is until there isn't someone standing
2 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	than him. I had you on last night and the Arsenal fan, he was blind.	You don't	know what that wee lad is sitting there, talking to you. I
3 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	to do and occasionally that's not going to work. When you go out and	you don't	do what your manager wants and you don't play as a
4 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	and occasionally you have a bad day and you draw one one with Forest, but	you don't	have a bad day and lose seven nil. So do you seriously
5 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	of those Newcastle players would go into any of those squads? Absolutely, you're right.	You don't	know, but I would say from the argument it's always gonna
6 DamonASTWon26C.txt	saying in the dressing room or in training was actually causing negativity among the players,	you don't	know. All I can say is that I'm absolutely buzzing. It'
7 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	work. When you go out and you don't do what your manager wants and	you don't	play as a team, which is what he's done today. It'
8 BenIIVWon47C.txt	it's a different ballgame wherever you play, but you've got to believe. If	you don't,	then there's no point watching the match. Yeah, I mean like
9 CarlASTWon51C.txt	clubs. Look what's happening to Everton. You don't get Everton, occasionally you will,	you don't	get the Villa fans phoning in, these heritage clubs, phoning in. And
10 CarlASTWon51C.txt	suffered and you know, there's lots of clubs. Look what's happening to Everton.	You don't	get Everton, occasionally you will, you don't get the Villa fans
11 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	is number one to gurr, he's the champion and he pushed the lines, man.	You don't	do that, I don't think Robbie even did that. You don'
12 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	lines, man. You don't do that, I don't think Robbie even did that.	You don't	push the lines, man. No, I don't think he should be
13 PeterNEWWon38C.txt	No, don't go 'mhm', they're a good team, but that's another thing.	You don't	want to talk about Mr Cleeve on the radio right now. I

Figure 2.3: Winners Corpus 'you don't' concordance.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	TomMCILost27C.txt	thinking 'oh, we've got to give it to him again' or whatever, you know,	you don't	know what's going on. So I wasn't looking forward to
2	TomMCILost27C.txt	possibly, the point you said about Haaland, is that playing on the player's mind?	You don't	know if they're thinking 'oh, we've got to give it
3	MarkLEILost30C.txt	be any in between. Well, if you don't want to give him money, because	you don't	trust him because I've got to be quite honest, some of
4	MarkLEILost30C.txt	in a lot of trouble like they are. So get a new man in if	you don't	trust him. Yeah, that's the thing. The only name and I
5	ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	know, I mean, what do you expect if you get rid of a manager and	you don't	have another one lined up and you're prepared to let the
6	BrianLEILost43C.txt	offside trap completely and you'll have far more entertaining football. But you would, because	you don't	need these silly linesmen because they can't even get a corner
7	AndyBRILost7C.txt	striker did that to their defender that goal would have been ruled out straight away.	You don't	push a player just to get past them. He flattened him to
8	AndyBRILost7C.txt	their defenders that goal would have been disallowed. It is a push on a player.	You don't	push, you can't, because you're not allowed to. Any tackle
9	AndyBRILost7C.txt	t push a player just to get past them. He flattened him to the ground.	You don't	think it was a foul? That's fair if that's your
10	MarkLEILost30C.txt	to back him. I don't think there can be any in between. Well, if	you don't	want to give him money, because you don't trust him because
11	MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	a Scottish kiss on someone and I bet you regretted doing that, didn't you?	You don't	think you did? Well, you must've done something you regretted. Yeah.

Figure 2.4: *Losers Corpus 'you don't' concordance.*

Once again, the use of the second person 'you' shows an impersonal function when collocating with 'don't', but more often targets a specific entity as an attribution of blame. The impersonal function usually occurs when the caller wants to express doubt, collocating in a longer string of 'you don't know' in the top concordances. The implication of this use is that it is impossible for a layperson to come to conclusions in the scenario. It is, of course, not the intention of the caller to represent themselves as a layperson and is instead to outline a negative stance, referring to the unintelligible chaos at the club, where even expert fans have no better understanding than a less knowledgeable supporter. As for the attribution of blame, it is a goal of phone-in callers to assess who was worthy of blame or praise. The assessed entities encompass the players, managers, owners, and officiators, shown by 2, 6, and 10 in the LC. A handful of collocations add to the discourse about refereeing decisions, using a 'you don't' construction as a way of making the rules seem clearer, including 6, 7, 8, and 9 in the LC. The negative stances suggest that certain players were cheating, which deflects from the poor result suffered by the callers' teams. The hosts are referred to sparingly, showing an unwillingness to challenge the power imbalance. In the LC, interrogatives are also deployed in the use of this structure in 9 and 11, which is less face-threatening for the hosts, because they can easily disagree when they answer the question. Alternatively, if the point was put across via a declarative, it would be more difficult for the addressee to interrupt and refute the claim.

4.1.3 Experience Markers

Table 5.1: *Winners Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
beat		16		
lose		19		
played		5		8
saw	14			
tried				7
win		9		

Table 5.2: *Losers Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
backed		17		
chose				9

finished		23		
gambled				10
lost		8		
played		22		
turned	27			
won		9		

Experience markers are perhaps the most inclusive of the collocation categories. I propose this term as a description of the types of verbs that are tangible and able to be proved or disproved. They relate to physical experiences that are not mental. As with auxiliary verbs, their function is hybrid and pertains to both stance and credibility. The distinction between these functions is simple, with stance being invoked through the collocations of verbs relating to the actual sport. On the other hand, credibility is instead concerned with verbs that are more general and have nothing inherently to do with football, which are analysed in Section 4.2. As a result of the high number of potential verbs that this category could include, there is little overlap between corpora. The frequency of the collocations is not particularly high, but they tend to occur in the ‘we’ and ‘they’ environments.

The only comparable collocation is the ‘we played’ structure. It occurs infrequently in the LC, but interestingly is not indicative of a negative stance in 1 and 3. Despite appearing rarely, these callers attempt to find a positive when the result was poor, describing how the team played well or a tactical change that had an impact. This is also infrequent in the WC, but there is again a noticeable lack of negative stances being taken. Most of the collocations occur when a different team is the object of the verb phrase, where the recent game is compared to a historical one.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 CarlASTWon51C.txt	There were probably fifty thousand people in there, it was just cramped, people walking, when	we played	Barcelona in 1977, I think or '78. And we were two nil down with ten
2 CarlASTWon51C.txt	never walked out, I was with my dad, I was about seven years old when	we played	Barcelona. There were probably fifty thousand people in there, it was just cramped,
3 MichaelLWWon48C.txt	expecting today, the performance I saw. It was completely a million miles away from when	we played	Brentford. We didn't turn up. When we played Brighton, we didn't
4 MichaelLWWon48C.txt	a million miles away from when we played Brentford. We didn't turn up. When	we played	Brighton, we didn't turn up. When I was at Wolves, we just
5 MichaelLWWon48C.txt	beat United seven nil today. Chris, yeah, I think it has been burnout, I mean,	we played	every game last year right to the last minute. We were in every
6 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	we had some great results. And I just think watching the game today, yes, but	we played	okay in the first half but we lack organisation in the second half
7 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	this point onwards they will fall to pieces. No, they played really good football. No,	we played	really well. We made loads of chances and what happens in football is
8 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	were super organised, right, we had it, we had an identity, we had an organisation,	we played	some really good yes, okay, it was counter attacking, but when we went
9 PhilARSWon35C.txt	because Tottenham are so hit and miss. I knew we would get a result today.	We played	them off the park and we were just our brilliant self again. And
10 StuartNFOWon21C.txt	we got, you know, the arm was outstretched, to save him from going offside, but	we played	well, Chris, and the enthusiasm in the team. I mean, I sit in

Figure 3.1: Winners Corpus ‘we played’ concordance

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JedMCILost38C.txt	seem to press well. We're better without a forward, that was proved last season.	We played	better without a forward. It's gonna be close. Yes.
2 TonyMCILost18C.txt	two seasons. Once Sergio Aguerro went, we've got nobody else and that's how	we played	it, the false number nine. So yeah, we've just taken a little
3 MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	the team of the eighties. I mean, it's a long time ago. I thought	we played	really well today, we lost, fair play, but I actually thought we showed
4 JimTOTLost33C.txt	got man of the match. It was like we didn't play that badly, but	we played	the second half and the issue I've got is it was a
5 DerekLEELost3C.txt	have gone out and got a striker because all they did, Rodrigo, if you remember,	we played	Tuesday night or Wednesday night and then Rodrigo got injured, then they were

Figure 3.2: Losers Corpus ‘we played’ concordance.

4.1.4 Modal Verbs

Table 6.1: Winners Corpus modal verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
-----------	---	----	-----	------

can	16	8	4	
could		21	8	
'd	17	15		
'll	9	7		
might		22		
should		6		
will				11
would	6	18		

Table 6.2: *Losers Corpus modal verbs*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
can	14	5	4	
could		12		8
couldn't		21		
'd	5	16		
'll	17	6		5
should		14		6
will		10		
would	11			

Wiggins (2017, p. 173) defines modal verbs as verbs that implicate the speaker’s degree of ability, obligation, intention, or permission to be able to perform an activity. As with auxiliary verbs, there is a limited repertoire of verbs available to the speaker, so there is little difference between the corpora for these verbs themselves. The majority fall in the ‘we’ environment, with little variety in the frequencies of the collocations. A more striking difference, however, is the variation between the verbs that collocate with the third person ‘they’ pronoun, with ‘should’ and ‘could’ appearing in the LC but not WC. A limitation of AntConc is how it splits negated contractions into two words, meaning some verbs cannot be identified in a collocation list, such as the distinction between ‘can’ and ‘can’t’.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	gonna happen is, you see the teams around us, they know we've done it,	we can	do it and we've done it before and I won't say
2 BenLIVWon47C.txt	we've got to change from doubters to believers, you know, and I totally think	we can	do that. No, I think ninety five percent is a bit of a
3 MoCHEWon42C.txt	Potter now when I think it's more of a backwards step. I think if	we can	get Europa League football this season, I'm hoping, that will be a
4 JohnnyMCiWon55C.txt	Champions League this year purely because of Erling Haaland, I think, is Real Madrid. If	we can	get past Real Madrid, I think we win it. And I know that'
5 JoshARSWon39C.txt	re gonna lose this, our lead is only going to be two points". But if	we can	grab a point it'll be three at least but to turn that
6 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	needs to go in January. That's what four, five hundred k a week saved,	we can	maybe go and get the likes of Ivan Toney and now we're
7 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	I have to say that he's been brilliant this season. I would say that	we can	push towards the top ten, I wouldn't say any higher than that
8 PaulLEiWon24C.txt	stuff like that and he's found his feet a bit now and then hopefully	we can	recruit in January again.
9 MoCHEWon42C.txt	he'd had the summer transfer window, and early next season, I think, is when	we can	start saying is Potter the right man for Chelsea. I think this season,
10 PatrickARSWon37C.txt	I do, but I know that it's not a shoo in. Now, of course	we can	win it but I would say the game against Manchester United coming up
11 GlynTOTWon3C.txt	you very much, Chris, we didn't rate you very highly. No, to be fair,	we can'	t even push, because Arsenal are gonna fade away. They always do. Even
12 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	I just want you to tell me who is the best manager in Manchester. And	we can'	t talk about ten Hag in the Champions League because he never got
13 BenCRYWon50C.txt	percent, and Brighton. Mate, I'm a Palace fan who lives in Brighton, of course	we can.	My house is probably in trouble. I don't know.

Figure 4.1: *Winners Corpus 'we can' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JamesEVELost28C.txt	Lampard, did you say? It's not all on him. I generally don't think	we can	afford to sack him. I think he would have gone after Brighton and
2 JamesEVELost28C.txt	him, I think he'd have been gone by now. I just don't think	we can	afford to sack him. For Moshiri to come out in midweek and back
3 AlexASTLost9C.txt	clearly out of reach. I don't think the club is in a position where	we can	aim that high, frankly, I think we would need to see some form
4 JimTOTLost33C.txt	is Arsenal. The problem we've got at Spurs is Levy seems to think that	we can	buy trophies. He tried it with Mourinho, it didn't work, he's
5 JamieCHELost19C.txt	just needs that time and I think we're going to do well. I think	we can	do well.
6 LeoMUNLost45C.txt	as long as we do respond, alright, I think we'll be fine. I think	we can	finish in the top four and I think we can go for one
7 EmmaCHELost54C.txt	numerous times. But that's probably one of the biggest wins Chelsea women have. If	we can	get past Barcelona because they're more in form. Yeah, I have more
8 LeoMUNLost45C.txt	ll be fine. I think we can finish in the top four and I think	we can	go for one of the cups, hopefully, but top four and already a
9 VernonCHELost22C.txt	do, we've got this sort of recall that goes back so many decades, that	we can	recall every player, every debut. This is what football fans are. This is
10 MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	always gonna be a mid table team. You know, we're gonna be there. If	we can	stay up, for me, that's a bonus and anyone thinks we're
11 PatLIVLost29C.txt	but at times you just think, "well, where are they?" We don't look like	we can	win games ugly anymore, which we did last season. Well, you took the
12 JimEVELost17C.txt	gonna play him every week. But we've had patience, we've had enough patience,	we can't	t afford to have patience with managers. We need somebody who's gonna
13 JamieCHELost19C.txt	what would happen to us, who knows, but it's all about moving forward and	we can't	t be looking back. Maybe. Obviously we're used to winning trophies, but
14 MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	brilliant manager and I don't want anyone to have a go at him. But	we can't	t compete with the wages, that's the problem. It's down to
15 LeeCHELost51C.txt	dead. That's finished. There's no chance. That game's over. It's finished.	We can't	t defend, we can't score, it's finished. Look at Roy Hodgson.
16 BrianWOLLost12C.txt	t seem to be cutting it at Premier League level. I do believe now that	we can't	t exist until New Year with an interim coach. The situation is so
17 AlexASTLost9C.txt	promoted and earn his career there. I think I'd rather see Villa go, if	we can't	t get the top quality in we'd all love, Sean Dyche short
18 LeeCHELost51C.txt	There's no chance. That game's over. It's finished. We can't defend,	we can't	t score, it's finished. Look at Roy Hodgson. Look at when he'
19 JamesEVELost28C.txt	s off the table now Watkins is injured, so who are we going to get?	We can't	t afford anyone. Today, we backed that team. At half past one we
20 KevinWOLLost15C.txt	bring back, well I'll bring him in, I would approach for Sean Dyche. If	we can't	t get Nuno I'd go for Sean Dyche. I know they're

Figure 4.2: Losers Corpus 'we can' concordance.

The concordance lines for 'we can' show that it is negated frequently in the LC, in examples between 12 and 20. When this is not the case, the verb phrase is qualified in the left context with the verb 'don't', as well as conditional clauses. The level of ability implied by using the verb 'can' is low, compared to the negated 'can't', which is much more certain. This phrase is concerned with the team's ability to succeed, but there is also a prevalent semantic field of money. The caller takes a stance where they lament the funds available in 1, 2, 12, and 19, another sign of pessimism as they bring into question the efficiency with which their club is run. The collocation appears less in the WC, but the negativity about money is not present. The theme is more hopeful, with the callers employing the lower level of modality as a method of hedging to highlight what is possible, but perhaps not likely, as in 1, 2, and 10.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 RickMUNWon56C.txt	the years, de Gea has made the saves and kept United in games in matches	they should	have lost and I would say that, for several seasons, United really only
2 RickMUNWon56C.txt	in the Premier League, de Gea was making the saves and keeping United in games	they should	have lost, so United need to keep him, he needs to sign his

Figure 4.3: Winners Corpus 'they should' concordance.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	fifth and in the Europa League to be fair, and it's just a shambles.	They should	be doing better, but then there's no one at the helm. You
2 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	it all goes wrong and sometimes they overstep the mark and it's quite right	they should	be punished for it. But let's not, you know, take this out
3 PennyNEWLost46C.txt	be encouraging a lot of the Manchester supporters to call up but I mean, honestly,	they should	be surprised at how quiet they are. So when you talk about who
4 ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	could turn the team around a bit because obviously their confidence on the floor and	they should	be trying harder. You're right Chris, but just give that a go
5 DerekLEELost3C.txt	the best strikers in the country and this time, I mean, the load of tosh,	they should	have gone out and got a striker because all they did, Rodrigo, if
6 JimEVELost17C.txt	me today, I convinced them to go over. They have season tickets and they say	they should	ve gone to see Celtic, but anyway, the thing that I would like

Figure 4.4: Losers Corpus 'they should' concordance.

As for the 'they should' concordance, this shows a more extreme emotional reaction as a stronger level of modality is used. It occasionally shows a shift in pronoun use where the club or players that would usually be referred to as 'we', have changed to show their discontent after losing. Ellison (2014) concluded that, in political radio programmes, pronoun use can be simply reduced to 'we' referring to the perceived protagonist and 'they' referring to the antagonists. These attributions of blame illustrate

the disdain towards entities that were previously perceived as ‘protagonists’, where their effort is brought into question; something very basic. The goal of these callers is to vent these emotions and take the stance that something needs to change. The fifth example is directed at the club's decision makers, with the implication being that the fans do not back them and use pronouns to distance themselves from these poor decisions.

4.1.5 Communication Markers

Table 7.1: Winners Corpus communication markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
heard	21			
said	13			
told	19			

Table 7.2: Losers Corpus communication markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
laughed			6	
listened	21			
said	8			
say	24			
talked	28			

The final collocation category that invokes stance is communication markers. This category includes all dialogue and conversation where there is an implied speaker and listener, resulting in a preference for past tense as the communication has usually been completed. Most of these appear in the environment of the pronoun ‘I’. This is one of the rarer categories, with the simple past tense verb ‘said’ being the only marker that features in both corpora with any regularity.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	I love him, he's like Bill Shankly all over again. I love him. Like	I said	to you Robbie a long time ago, I love Bobby Firmino and I'
2 MohammedMCiWon57C.txt	listen to me. Do you remember when they beat Brighton away? Do you Remember? And	I said	to you we're coming for this league, Robbie, I told you, this
3 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	like, you know, but I asked him about the young lad Garnacho, you know, and	I said	to him, "is he playing today?" He smiled, he said he's in
4 JilCHEWon43C.txt	playing as a team. I think they're playing as individuals and that's why	I said	to your producer I think Chelsea needs Emma Hayes and I mean the
5 JilCHEWon43C.txt	without him. I'll give him a bit of credit. I feel sorry for him.	I said	that to your producer. I feel sorry for him. I think he's
6 TomASTWon19C.txt	has just been obliterated. The last time that I phoned your show, a year ago,	I said	that we should go and get Steven Gerrard and I remember you two
7 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	to cheer about the last couple of seasons, so we need to be realistic. So	I said	at the start of the season if we finish fifth and won a
8 EdMUNWon36C.txt	they? They've got us, they've got Fulham and they've got Brentford. Brentford,	I said	Brighton to your producer on the phone, but Brentford, that's not a
9 MichaelIIVWon48C.txt	object. I went in full tilt and gave Robertson a really good dressing down because	I said	his performances to date, up until a couple of weeks ago, have been
10 RichardMUNWon27C.txt	as I say, still have the League Cup, so your treble's on. I know	I said	last year when we beat Leeds that the quad was on, but this
11 DanielNEWon18C.txt	a fantastic job and the manager who I would like to equate him to, and	I said	this to my dad the other day when we were watching the Everton
12 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	me "we need to do this, we need to do that, buy this, buy that",	I said	yes, but we've got the right man in charge. I love him,
13 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	the squad for the day. He said to me, "what do you think of him?"	I said "	I've been following him" I said, you know, from youth level, following
14 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	you know, from youth level, following him in the last few years, you know, and	I said "	what do you think as the manager and the coaching staff? What do
15 DavidCHEWon11C.txt	He's probably a big fan of yours. We're devastated for him, but as	I said,	Thiago Silva, is absolutely fantastic. A lot of people say we wish we
16 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	to me, "what do you think of him?" I said "I've been following him"	I said,	you know, from youth level, following him in the last few years, you

Figure 5.1: Winners Corpus ‘I said’ concordance.

File	Left Context	He	Right Context
1 SimonWHULost41C.txt	us. It doesn't seem like it to us. When he goes out to, as	I said	before, the big clubs and he sets up not to lose and clearly
2 TomMCLost27C.txt	thought there was only gonna be one winner here and I wasn't surprised. As	I said	before, you can't complain as a City fan. Thanks, have a good
3 JimTOTlost33C.txt	Mourinho, it didn't work, he's trying it with Conte, it's not working.	I said	before, you'll remember me, I said get Klinsmann and Sheringham in or
4 TomMCLost27C.txt	that "come on let's get a second, come on let's get a third."	I said	last night, you know, you obviously have the best conversations in the pub
5 LeeCHELost51C.txt	you laughed at me. I have to say you're not laughing now, are you?	I said	last time there's more chance of Chelsea getting relegated than winning the
6 LeeCHELost51C.txt	asked me for a percentage. You said what's the percentage of Chelsea getting relegated.	I said	last time, I said fifty one percent relegation, forty nine percent Champions League.
7 DavidLELost42C.txt	when we had lost five two at Brighton and called for Brendan Rodgers to go.	I said	to Chris, we've gotta give him more time. I then came on
8 MichaelCHELost16C.txt	so disappointed, they really do, I don't think he knows his best formation. As	I said	to the guy who took the phone call, he said "it's a
9 DannyFULost24.txt	and dropped seven points. In the league, we would be fifth. No. Fantastic job. Like	I said	to you, I think we're overachieving. There's going to be a
10 TomMCLost27C.txt	said last night, you know, you obviously have the best conversations in the pub and	I said	I don't feel confident. I said I feel United are on a
11 TomMCLost27C.txt	have the best conversations in the pub and I said I don't feel confident.	I said	I feel United are on a slow but very steady upward trajectory under
12 TomLELost52C.txt	was no plan b to get us out of the mess we were in. And	I said	after we got rid of Rodgers, I hope they've got someone in
13 LeeCHELost51C.txt	haven't. There's no upturn at all. We're terrible. No, this is what	I said	before, I didn't want Frank back. We need De Zerbi. We need
14 LeeCHELost51C.txt	percentage. You said what's the percentage of Chelsea getting relegated. I said last time,	I said	fifty one percent relegation, forty nine percent Champions League. Now I'm saying
15 JimTOTlost33C.txt	trying it with Conte, it's not working. I said before, you'll remember me,	I said	get Klinsmann and Sheringham in or at the very least get Pochettino back
16 MohammedWHULost21C.txt	Chris? Do you remember what happened last time, when I talked to you last week?	I said	that we have to beat Palace. Yeah, but look, we lost to Palace
17 MichaelLVLost6C.txt	you must've done something you regretted. Yeah. Well I just think it was, as	I said	a massive game for us to beat Manchester City. Today Notts Forest were
18 BenLELost13C.txt	going to play him why is Gelhardt not playing off him, for instance, or as	I said	Gnonto who seems to have arrived in Leeds and gone missing? We've
19 AndrewTOTlost40C.txt	beaten Man City, we've beaten Chelsea. Yeah. So what I was saying, so as	I said	last time I was on the show I was very effusive about the
20 BrianLELost43C.txt	not good enough. They've never kicked a football in their lives, that's what	I said	people like yourself and Robbie, professional footballers should come back as referees. Just
21 JedMCLost38C.txt	all that injury time. Fifteen, twenty minutes, he must've been. Well, I mean, like	I said	the thing is we don't press as well with Haaland in the
22 AlexASTLost9C.txt	comes in and works. So I'd rather have someone with Premiership experience. So, as	I said	this is as bad as 2015/2016 as far as I'm concerned, the way

Figure 5.2: Losers Corpus 'I said' concordance.

The goal of this collocation is to invoke and repeat a stance that was taken previously in another conversation that is worth repeating to a larger audience. These types of conversations can act as the breeding ground for football phone-in discussions, as they raise questions or interesting points for adjudication. The callers do not show a change in opinion since the original stance was taken. When a previous conversation is revisited, there is, of course, an implied listener. The identity of this participant can be beneficial for creating an interesting discussion, but this is a more individual phenomenon where patterns are harder to ascertain. A pattern that is evident, however, is the repetition of the callers' point to the producers, such as 8 in the LC and 4 and 5 in the WC. The producers ultimately choose the callers allowed to put their views on air, so by invoking them as a participant, this implies that the producers considered the stances to be interesting and worth airing.

4.2 Building Credibility

As we have already seen, the primary use of pronouns is in constructions that outline stance. It is the prerogative of the hosts to undermine the callers, as good debate facilitates a good call. The constructions of stances need some basis, and the callers need to state their credentials and *why* they are qualified to talk on the topic. As recognised by Fitzgerald and Housely (2002, p. 597), callers provide authentication to their opinions. The listeners will know nothing about them other than the information from the opening sequence, so callers need to bring this into the conversation when advantageous.

4.2.1 Auxiliary Verbs

Table 8.1: Winners Corpus auxiliary verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	11	17		6
did		14		
didn't	25	13		10
do	22			

don't	4		11	
had		4		
'm/'re	2	1	2	1
've	5	2	5	2
was/were	8	3	17	3
wasn't/weren't				5

Table 8.2: Losers Corpus auxiliary verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	10			4
did				
didn't		15		13
don't	4	16	8	
had		9		
have		20		
haven't		7		12
'm/'re	2	2	2	1
've	6	1	3	2
was/were	14	3		3
wasn't/weren't				7

As discussed previously, auxiliary verbs functioned in collocations for both stance and credibility constructions. This distinction only becomes clear upon examination of the concordance lines. The above collocation table is a replica of the one fully analysed in the earlier chapter.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JillICHEWon43C.txt	How are you? I'm great, thanks. Did you get it right? Well,	I'm a	season ticket holder. I didn't go today because I'm so
2 PeterMUNWon33C.txt	I am Robbie, yeah. Well, I'm not just a fan,	I'm a	season ticket holder. Absolutely. It was a fantastic day and it's
3 PaulBOUWon54C.txt	Oh, great, couldn't be better. I know, it's amazing.	I'm a	bit concerned though, because you said that we might stay up now.
4 ShazARSWon41C.txt	s decision not going our way and it's a human error. But, I mean,	I'm a	blind person, but to get VAR decisions wrong in the last three
5 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	got nothing to complain about' but when you watch the quality of that football, honestly,	I'm a	Church of England vicar, right, and that was like the Easter weekend
6 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	So what, you won a league cup. My point is that we're going nowhere.	I'm a	Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan from 1973. We're going
7 BenCRYWon50C.txt	of the National League. He's got football problems. A hundred percent, and Brighton, Mate,	I'm a	Palace fan who lives in Brighton, of course we can. My house

Figure 6.1: Winners Corpus 'I'm a' concordance

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 TomMCILost27C.txt	and as a squad they seemed to have more desire. I think they did, seriously.	I'm a	City fan. No, they seemed to want it more and we seemed
2 TonyMCILost18C.txt	I'm being smug, I'm not. I have full faith in Pep Guardiola, but	I'm a	City fan from thirty years ago, so I love the guy. I
3 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	people have got no patience and are just too quick to shoot people down. Sorry,	I'm a	grassroots manager. I manage my son in an under eighteen team. I'
4 PatLIVLost29C.txt	quick to look at, well, 'oh we're on a bad run, sack the manager'.	I'm a	great believer, you know, form is temporary, class is permanent and Jurgen
5 MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	they knocked us out in the Champions League. They beat us over two legs. So	I'm a	Liverpool fan. Yeah, I love Liverpool. When I saw them play I
6 DannyTOTLost36C.txt	Spurs fan. Believe you me, I've gone and watched Spurs lose for enough years.	I'm a	proper Spurs fan. I actually think the problems start at the top
7 BernardWHULost32C.txt	has been dropping off a cliff in the league and I go to home games,	I'm a	season ticket holder. The last quarter of last season, you could already
8 BrianLEILost43C.txt	was six inches away. He was protecting his face. It's just ludicrous. No, because	I'm a	twenty five year season ticket holder. That's it. I've finished

Figure 6.2: Losers Corpus 'I'm a' concordance.

These concordance patterns show the context for the construction 'I'm a', which is the principal way of invoking identity. There are different categories of identities, each going to various lengths to provide

expert credentials that allow them to be judged as such (Kilby & Horowitz, 2013). The first of these is invoking a ‘season ticket holder’ identity in 1 and 2 in the WC and 7 and 8 in the LC, which shows a certain level of devotion regardless of their team’s fortunes. The act of attending games every week is perceived favourably and is a key tool for enhancing credibility, qualifying the caller’s stance as they refer to the evidence of their own eyes. There is a hierarchy within the fandoms themselves, suggesting that these identities ensure the callers to position themselves at the top. Foster and Kilby (2023, p. 556) refer to these as ‘mundane discursive manoeuvres’ that ‘elevate a narrow version of this identity’. This narrowed identity, in a football context, is the sense of entitlement these match-going supporters have; there is nothing that inherently means that more casual fans cannot form the same opinions as season ticket holders. There is another category of identities, characterised by having little reference to football, including 4 and 5 in the WC. Fitzgerald and Housely (2002, p. 586) corroborate that ‘there is a layer of identity membership that is not topic orientated’. They are not obsolete, helping to create an authentic and memorable call, invoking a more specific identity that few callers can stake a claim to. Despite appearing minor, the deployment of these identities is key in helping to ground the call in reality. When an element of anonymity is at play, credibility is built when the participant situates themselves ‘as a ‘real’ person’ (Vasquez, 2014, cited in Jacknick & Avni, 2017, p. 62). It is theoretically possible for anyone to call up and say anything, regardless of whether it is what they believe. These seemingly unrelated identities add an element of accountability to the caller that makes it seem as if what they say is a more irrefutable opinion. With all these identities, the listeners sympathise with one who shares an identity with themselves (Jautz, 2014, p. 22), so there is always potential for credibility to be built when these constructions are deployed.

A conspicuous pattern is that shown by the concordance for ‘I’m just’. As for the denotative meaning of the adverb ‘just’, there is an element of politeness and an unwillingness not to overrepresent, especially if that experience is not universal. Meanwhile, the first three winning concordances can be attributed to the callers positioning themselves as match-going, by referring to them travelling home from the stadium. For many fans, and especially away fans, this is part of the experience; they will drive home and think about what they have seen, so sometimes they might want to share their thoughts with a larger audience and decide to phone the programme. An element of the adverb is time-bound, as they were only *just* there. This links to fan hierarchy, because a fan’s status is undermined when they leave matches early, therefore it is beneficial for callers to suggest that they stayed until the end of the match. The advantages of callers positioning themselves as match-going have already been discussed and this is another construction that allows them to be perceived as experts, but the frequency with which it appears implies that they also want to appear as experts of the phone-in genre. Foster and Kilby (2023) posit that speakers who construct their identity in accordance with norms trump the arguments offered by other speakers, so it is beneficial for callers to hint that they frequently listen to the programme and hear other callers use this construction. The lack of left concordance context shows that it often occurs at the beginning of the calls. Hutchby (1999) explains this as he notices that openings allow the callers to align themselves with the identities they want to perform. The match-going fans deem that identity to be integral in building their credibility, so they offer these identities as a prelude to the stance they take in the call and means that they are immediately protected from having that aspect brought into question.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 DamonASTWon26C.txt	Yeah absolutely amazing, buzzing.	I'm just	on the way back now, in the car, but yeah, a really,
2 DavidCHEWon11C.txt	Hello mate,	I'm just	on the way back from Villa Park. All I've rung up
3 MichaelEVEWon15C.txt		I'm just	on my way home from Goodison. I mean, I really rang in
4 NickTOTWon1C.txt	won, don't get me wrong, and I'm glad that they gave it but	I'm just	saying I saw it and I don't think it was a
5 RickMUNWon56C.txt	Good evening. First time caller to the show.	I'm just	saying that David de Gea deserves to be Man United's top
6 ShazARSWon41C.txt	a row. I think this will be a bigger achievement than that. Would you agree?	I'm just	saying in terms of achievement. Yes, one Premier League in isolation, but
7 MatthewCHEWon40C.txt	But he's just proved to me that, I mean, I'm not being funny,	I'm just	a fan, humbly, and I'm thirty nine years old and I
8 SimonBRWWon52C.txt	job? Absolutely not. Well, maybe, who knows? And the appointment of Frank Lampard, who knows,	I'm just	going with what I've heard. I mean, so yeah, all I
9 DeanLIVWon46C.txt	How are you doing, Robbie? How are you doing, Chris? Yeah, absolutely and	I'm just	leaving Anfield now, actually. My question, really, was to you, Chris, because
10 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	in a nutshell. Crucifixion on Friday, resurrection on Sunday. It was painful at times and	I'm just	trying to believe what people tell me, trying to believe that we

Figure 6.3: *Winners Corpus 'I'm just' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	I'm very well, thank you. How are you? I think	I'm just	a bit fed up with the whole culture of all of us
2 VernonCHELost22C.txt	to anybody. It was just one of those things that sometimes happens, you know. Well,	I'm just	saying that this is the sort of passion that fans have for
3 BillBRILost25C.txt	shocked. Yes, Solly March. I just want to say great show, I love the show.	I'm just	shocked today. I'm still in shock now because that's not

Figure 6.4: *Losers Corpus 'I'm just' concordance.*

4.2.2 Experience Markers

Table 9.1: *Winners Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
bottled				4
broke	29			
got		11		
lived	27			
remember			10	
went	24	10		

Table 9.2: *Losers Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
gave		19		
regretted			7	
remember	19			

The collocation for experience markers is easier to separate between stance and credibility, with the credibility being constructed by verbs that appear to not be related to football. The potential verbs that could fit into this category are vast, so there are few parallels between the corpora. Many are part of individual anecdotes offered by callers to build credibility by invoking certain identities, hence they rank lowly.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MohammedMCWon57C.txt	bottled the FA Cup with Giggs going through everyone, do you remember, Robbie? And now,	they bottled	the Europa League, Robbie. Europa League, I'm not even there, Robbie. Robbie,
2 MohammedMCWon57C.txt	United, when Hasselbaink scored and they gave United the treble. Do you remember that? And	they bottled	the FA Cup with Giggs going through everyone, do you remember, Robbie? And
3 MohammedMCWon57C.txt	bottle job mentality. We know that, Robbie, you remember them. Alex Ferguson, all those times	they bottled	the league, with two games to go against Leeds United, when Hasselbaink scored
4 JohnnyMCWon55C.txt	last year, this time last year. They had top four in their hands and then	they bottled	it. I think it's the same thing. I think it's all

Figure 7: *Winners Corpus 'they bottled' concordance.*

Despite the low frequency of these collocations, the concordance of ‘they bottled’ still raises an interesting phenomenon that is present in modern football discourse. In the literature concerning discourse as a social practice, Fairclough (1989, p. 11) introduces ‘members’ resources’, which are prototypes for typical narratives. These are ‘socially determined’, so can be affected by factors most relevant to the communities. Mercer (2007, p. 108) notes that communities offer their members ‘a history’, which is certainly a predominant factor in determining football discourse. One of these available factors is rivalry; it is not enough to support one team, but fans also need to actively engage in the dislike and mockery of rival teams to bolster their expert credentials. Teams gain certain reputations due to their typical performances over the course of this history and one of the most negative reputations is that of ‘bottlers’, when they routinely relinquish good positions in individual games and across seasons. This is demonstrated by the above concordance, a construction only used in the WC, suggesting that it is only deployed when the callers are holders of linguistic power. Had their team lost, they would not have the grounds to mock their rivals this way. It is evident that the football community is significant in determining attitudes and beliefs towards issues, as supported by Chichon (2020, p. 7). The callers themselves would not have been the ones to choose a rivalry to pursue, but engaging in the discourse determines how credible they appear.

4.2.3 Politeness and Address

Table 10.1: *Winners Corpus politeness and address*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
alright			9	
doing			12	
guys			7	

Table 10.2: *Losers Corpus politeness and address*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
alright			5	

The final collocation category is that of politeness and address markers. The dichotomy of the phone call results in phatic communication between host and caller. This type of communication is indicated by second person pronouns, as found by Bednarek (2014) in a radio phone-in corpus and, in this case, is limited to collocating with only ‘you’.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 EdMUNWon36.txt	s a Manchester United fan. How are you Ed? C: How are you doing fellas?	You alright?	Alright thanks, can you win it, Ed? C: What's that fellas? Can
2 GlynTOTWon3.txt	Right then, Glyn is a Spurs fan, how are you, Glyn? C: Hello mate,	you alright?	Glyn, you must have had potato bravas in a tapas. C: Pardon? Never
3 MikeLIVWon8.txt	Mike, you're a Liverpool fan. C: Hello lads,	you alright?	Hi Mike. C: I've been at the game today, thanks for having
4 CarlASTWon51.txt	Carl, you're a Villa fan. C: Hello chaps, how are you doing,	you alright?	Alright Carl. C: Mate, can you tell by the tone of my voice
5 JoshARSWon39.txt	Josh, Arsenal fan. C: Hey boys,	you alright?	Josh, Josh. C: Come on, let's have it. Were you there today,
6 MoCHEWon42.txt	How are you? C: How are you, gents? Alright, Mo? C: Very well, how are	you, alright?	Well, you must be a bit upbeat Mo, after today? C: Yeah, it'
7 ThomasEVEWon16.txt	Thomas, how are you? Everton fan. C: Hi.	You alright,	gents? How is it going? Alright Thomas? C: Yeah, I've been to

Figure 8.1: *Winners Corpus ‘you alright’ concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MohammedWHULost21.txt	Mohammed, a West Ham fan. C: You alright guys? How are you, mate? C: Yeah,	<i>you alright,</i>	<i>Chris? Yeah,</i> very good thanks. That's nice to hear. C: Do you
2 LouisTOTLost35.txt		<i>You alright,</i>	<i>gents? How</i> are you? Okay, Louis, thank you. C: Good. Yeah, look, fair
3 JamesEVELost28.txt	James, you're an Everton fan. C: Hi, good evening,	<i>you alright?</i>	<i>How are</i> you, James? C: Oh well, I suppose there's only one
4 LeoMUNLost45.txt	Leo, a Manchester United fan. How are you, Leo? C: Hi, evening Robbie, evening Chris.	<i>You alright?</i>	<i>Leo,</i> quick question before we start, is Erik ten Hag the best manager
5 MohammedWHULost21.txt	Let's go to Mohammed, a West Ham fan. C:	<i>You alright</i>	<i>guys? How</i> are you, mate? C: Yeah, you alright, Chris? Yeah, very good
6 DeanMCLost5.txt	who is a Man City fan, how are you Dean? C: I'm alright, are	<i>you alright?</i>	<i>Yeah alright,</i> we've got you, Dean. C: I thought I would crawl

Figure 8.2: Losers Corpus ‘you alright’ concordance.

This concordance can be primarily explained by the conventionality of politeness. It is the norm for phone calls to begin with a greeting; hence, they can be found in the openings. It could be jarring for the caller to be overly eager and start with their point instead of establishing common ground through phatic communication. Due to its frequency in various forms, such as in the concordance above, the hosts will be expecting this sort of greeting, before then shifting into the main section of the call. Callers are ‘required to have a tacit understanding of the “rules” of debate and discussion’ (O’Sullivan, 2005, p. 732), so the callers should expect that they need to begin with a segment of this kind. Despite it being unlikely that host and caller would have ever interacted before, familiarity is present in the terms of reference used to refer to the hosts, which is because ‘callers “know” hosts from listening to their shows’ (Jautz, 2014, p. 20). The hosts might elicit the callers’ general views or might ask for an opinion on a specific topic of that programme. Sometimes this is football-related, but can also be light-hearted and humorous. This leads into credibility, as the levels to which the callers engage with the hosts’ prompts can give them support. According to Chichon (2020), the hosts could be viewed as experts and their support, or lack thereof, could be seen as significant. Their views on the stances taken by the callers can therefore influence the way those callers are perceived. Any callers who do not demonstrate forms of politeness during the openings already leave themselves vulnerable to a lack of host support, with any resulting criticism harming their credibility.

5 Conclusion

To return to the research questions outlined in the introduction, there are few differences in the pronoun use between callers whose teams won or lost. The collocation data can be categorised into six groups, and further classified into the themes of stance-taking and credibility. Phone-in callers will have a point they want to say on radio, which will express views on a variety of entities, such as the performance of their own team, their owners, or referees. Constructions that impart stances use a wide range of pronouns, to demonstrate the group of people that take that view. It might be limited to that speaker themselves, or they might want to show that it is commonly held and potentially obvious. The main difference, as could be expected, is that losers take more negative stances. A striking difference is the preference of losers to deploy third person pronouns with modal verbs. One might predict that unhappy supporters shift from ‘we’ to ‘they’ to describe their team, which is a feature found in the corpus, but is not common amongst all callers in similar scenarios. Over the course of the paper, it has emerged how important credibility is to what the callers say. The link between stance and credibility arises because, while callers can take any stance they wish, they might not be taken seriously. In that case, they use pronouns in credibility constructions to invoke identities that prove they have expert status, as both an expert of their team and an expert of the format of the programme. The result of the caller’s team has no effect on their deployment of credibility structures. They tend to be realised through the pronoun ‘I’, as callers are only concerned with managing their own credibility.

As for the limitations of the study, the collocation only focuses on the token directly to the right of the pronoun, resulting in potential patterns in different positions of the pronoun’s environment not

being found. The rationale for not including draws in the corpus was mentioned earlier, but it could still be interesting to compare with the other corpora and whether those callers aligned themselves with positive or negative stances. As with all corpus research, personal biases can affect the interpretations of the data identified by the analytical tools. I have my own personal experiences of the season, after following it closely myself. For example, stances that I might deem controversial or extreme might not be perceived as such by the caller and their fanbase. It is impossible to accurately comment on a speaker's intentions when using a certain utterance, but corpus methods show patterns that allow them to be interpreted more precisely.

Overall, this study has broken new ground by applying a CADS framework to analyse a football phone-in, a previously untested combination. The quantity of interesting findings suggest that this genre is worthy of further research to investigate its other aspects. The six collocation categories are versatile in their application and can be used to study and compare collocation across any topic a researcher wishes. The themes of stance and credibility will continue to be of interest and researchers will continue to study them to add to the comprehensive literature on their respective functions in discourse.

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7 Appendix

If you would like to request higher quality copies of the figures used throughout this paper, please contact up2063704@myport.ac.uk via email.

7.1 Appendix One: Participants Breakdown

Table A1: Full breakdown of participants’ information that determined corpus inclusion

Caller Name	Supported Team	Team Result	Date	Corpus Inclusion	Discard Reason
Nick	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Joe	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Glyn	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Ollie	Bournemouth	Drew	15 th October	No	Draw
Gareth	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Luke	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Derek	Celtic	Won	15 th October	No	Scottish team
Jo	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Matthew	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	

PROCEEDINGS OF ULAB XIV

Tom	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Bart	Manchester City	Did not play	15 th October	No	Did not play
Ryan	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Steve	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Steve	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Derek	Leeds	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
Greg	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Anthony	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Andy	Aston Villa	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
Mike	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Stampy	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Chris	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Amit	Manchester United	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Shaun	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Paul	Newcastle	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Logan	Birmingham	Won	16 th October	No	Championship team
Dean	Manchester City	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
David	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Adam	West Ham	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Gordon	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Steve	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Michael	Liverpool	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Matthew	Manchester City	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Steve	Manchester City	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Sam	Chelsea	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Andy	Manchester United	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Michael	Everton	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Andy	Brighton	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Simon	Liverpool	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	

UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX
5-7 APRIL 2024

Jay	Manchester United	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Thomas	Everton	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Derek	Celtic	Won	22 nd October	No	Scottish team
Alex	Aston Villa	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Adi	QPR	Won	22 nd October	No	Championship team
Duncan	Crystal Palace	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Carl	QPR	Won	22 nd October	No	Championship team
James	West Ham	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Brian	Wolves	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Dave	Aston Villa	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Ben	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Daniel	Newcastle	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Connor	Southampton	Drew	23 rd October	No	Draw
Damian	Tottenham	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Tom	Aston Villa	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Kevin	Wolves	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Ben	Watford	Won	23 rd October	No	Championship team
Josh	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	No	Ethical concerns
Gavin	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	No	Debates with previous caller
Michael	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Jayden	Newcastle	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Jim	Everton	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Stuart	Nottingham Forest	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Mark	Brentford	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Tony	Manchester City	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Jamie	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Terry	Everton	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Mohammed	West Ham	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
John	Tottenham	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Dave	Tottenham	Won	12 th November	No	Debates with previous caller
Vernon	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Brian	Celtic	Won	12 th November	No	Scottish team

PROCEEDINGS OF ULAB XIV

Jay	Manchester United	Did not play	12 th November	No	Did not play
Ollie	Wolves	Unfinished game	12 th November	No	Unfinished game
Paul	Leicester	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Aaron	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Damon	Aston Villa	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Richard	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Andrew	Brighton	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Aaron	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	No	Corpus balancing
Jake	Arsenal	Drew	13 th November	No	Draw
Danny	Fulham	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Lee	Burnley	Won	13 th November	No	Championship team
Paul			13 th November	No	Not talking about own team
Nigel	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Bill	Brighton	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Tracey	Tottenham	Won	13 th November	Yes	
John	Arsenal	Drew	13 th November	No	Draw
Chris	Liverpool	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Abdullah	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Reg	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Andrew	Brighton	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Tom	Manchester City	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
James	Everton	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Pat	Liverpool	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Mark	Leicester	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Emma	Nottingham Forest	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Lindon	Everton	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Peter	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Bernard	West Ham	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Shaz	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	

UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX
5-7 APRIL 2024

Jim	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Taz	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Phil	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Louis	Spurs	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Alan	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Ed	Manchester United	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Danny	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Patrick	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Patrick	Crystal Palace	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Ben	Middlesbrough	Won	15 th January	No	Championship team
Jed	Manchester City	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Shaun	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Peter	Newcastle	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Michael	Crystal Palace	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Josh	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Andrew	Tottenham	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Simon	West Ham	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
David	Leicester	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Jake	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Matthew	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Brian	Leicester	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Shaz	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Mo	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Jill	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Dan	QPR	Lost	4 th March	No	Championship team
Yaya	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Neil	Blackburn	Won	4 th March	No	Championship team
Ryan	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Michael	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Jamie	Manchester United	Lost	5 th March	Yes	

PROCEEDINGS OF ULAB XIV

Dean	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Ben	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Leo	Manchester United	Lost	5 th March	Yes	
Penny	Newcastle	Lost	5 th March	Yes	
Michael	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Dave	Manchester City	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Elaine	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Sanj	Arsenal	Won	5 th March	No	Not talking about own team
Rizwan	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Michael	Everton	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Christian	Tottenham	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Gordon	Newcastle	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Nick	Tottenham	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Hitesh	Leeds	Did not play	15 th April	No	Did not play
Ben	Crystal Palace	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Carl	Aston Villa	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Simon	Brighton	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Lee	Chelsea	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Josh	Manchester City	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Tom	Leicester	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Paul	Bournemouth	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Ben	Ipswich	Won	15 th April	No	League One Team
Johnny	Manchester City	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Aggie	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Adam	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Ivan	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Rhys	Nottingham Forest	Lost	16 th April	Yes	
Alex	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
James	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Rick	Manchester United	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Emma	Chelsea	Lost	16 th April	Yes	

John	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Neil	Norwich	Lost	16 th April	No	Championship team
Sanj	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Mohammed	Manchester City	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Michael	Nottingham Forest	Lost	16 th April	Yes	

7.2 Appendix Two: Collocation Tables

Table A2: *Winners Corpus 'I' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
think	1	171	44	861.940	4.200
'm	2	117	45	754.430	4.659
mean	3	72	31	462.529	4.663
don't	4	74	36	347.728	4.098
've	5	49	26	128.075	2.923
would	6	32	19	100.314	3.274
thought	7	16	15	70.280	3.983
was	8	42	20	63.757	2.104
'll	9	15	11	59.963	3.783
love	10	11	7	49.938	4.055
am	11	7	5	45.497	4.683
wanted	12	10	9	38.087	3.683
said	13	16	11	36.933	2.729
saw	14	7	6	36.120	4.321
agree	15	9	8	35.636	3.766
can	16	17	15	34.918	2.542
'd	17	9	8	35.636	3.531
feel	18	7	5	31.392	4.031
told	19	5	2	24.270	4.198
know	20	25	19	23.320	1.586
heard	21	5	3	20.438	3.835
do	22	16	14	20.019	1.889
just	23	18	14	16.402	1.568
went	24	6	5	15.048	2.876
didn't	25	7	7	13.052	2.403
knew	26	4	3	13.000	3.361
lived	27	2	2	12.989	4.683
reckon	28	2	2	12.989	4.683
broke	29	2	1	12.989	4.683

fully	30	2	1	12.989	4.683
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Table A3: *Winners Corpus 'we' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	66	32	337.872	4.602
've	2	66	28	315.286	4.407
were	3	50	26	247.102	4.523
had	4	17	10	61.793	3.759
played	5	10	7	45.710	4.359
should	6	9	5	38.856	4.207
'll	7	9	7	37.307	4.100
can	8	13	12	36.892	3.209
win	9	11	4	33.545	3.364
went	10	7	6	29.576	4.153
got	11	15	13	27.770	2.445
i	12	1	1	27.668	-4.106
didn't	13	8	7	27.641	3.650
did	14	8	6	25.348	3.452
'd	15	6	6	23.893	4.001
beat	16	5	4	21.913	4.252
are	17	10	10	17.740	2.387
would	18	9	4	17.160	2.498
lose	19	4	3	16.141	4.037
need	20	4	3	14.867	3.831
could	21	5	5	13.407	3.105
might	22	3	2	12.650	4.153
needed	23	2	1	12.136	5.153

Table A4: *Winners Corpus 'you' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
know	1	137	36	819.442	4.916
're	2	40	22	144.860	3.702
look	3	18	11	79.921	4.238
can	4	19	12	64.575	3.579
've	5	21	15	42.649	2.577
the	6	1	1	35.311	-4.397
guys	7	7	7	34.936	4.560
could	8	9	8	33.102	3.775
alright	9	7	7	32.499	4.367
remember	10	6	2	29.934	4.560
don't	11	13	8	24.458	2.466

doing	12	8	7	22.320	3.167
think	13	18	11	20.845	1.829
and	14	1	1	16.894	-3.546
you	15	1	1	14.857	-3.406
to	16	1	1	14.540	-3.383
were	17	10	7	13.603	2.024

Table A5: Winners Corpus 'they' collocates

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	39	21	213.616	5.002
've	2	22	13	85.140	3.981
were	3	15	13	56.799	3.945
bottled	4	4	2	33.334	6.574
weren't	5	4	2	27.297	5.896
are	6	8	7	22.246	3.224
tried	7	2	2	19.140	6.896
played	8	4	3	16.360	4.196
just	9	8	7	16.099	2.611
didn't	10	4	4	14.187	3.809
will	11	3	2	11.516	4.022

Table A6: Losers Corpus 'I' collocates

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
think	1	167	44	854.955	4.277
'm	2	113	41	764.501	4.788
mean	3	77	31	507.079	4.770
don't	4	73	37	324.270	4.012
'd	5	33	17	153.319	4.132
've	6	52	28	120.670	2.727
thought	7	17	11	87.189	4.352
said	8	22	15	81.085	3.633
just	9	29	20	58.124	2.507
am	10	6	5	39.866	4.788
would	11	15	12	37.702	2.888
believe	12	8	6	36.214	4.088
was	13	26	15	31.688	1.859
can	14	17	15	30.202	2.336
know	15	25	19	30.118	1.847
agree	16	7	5	27.622	3.788
'll	17	10	8	21.803	2.651
suppose	18	4	3	21.638	4.466

remember	19	6	4	21.331	3.566
feel	20	5	5	21.144	3.940
listened	21	3	3	19.923	4.788
hate	22	3	2	19.923	4.788
generally	23	3	2	19.923	4.788
say	24	10	9	18.997	2.438
love	25	5	5	16.480	3.410
hope	26	3	3	13.340	4.051
turned	27	3	1	13.340	4.051
talked	28	2	2	13.280	4.788
expected	29	2	2	13.280	4.788
personally	30	2	2	13.280	4.788

Table A7: Losers Corpus 'we' collocates

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
've	1	100	33	493.368	4.429
're	2	74	36	400.760	4.711
were	3	33	21	150.294	4.287
need	4	19	12	96.250	4.585
can	5	20	14	60.745	3.329
'll	6	14	11	54.231	3.894
haven't	7	10	7	52.684	4.698
lost	8	9	6	40.136	4.257
had	9	13	11	32.410	2.943
will	10	10	5	32.329	3.476
I	11	1	1	31.342	-4.256
could	12	9	9	30.554	3.587
won	13	7	5	29.417	4.106
should	14	9	8	27.557	3.359
didn't	15	9	7	26.256	3.257
'd	16	9	8	23.265	3.016
backed	17	3	1	23.083	5.546
don't	18	13	10	21.563	2.281
gave	19	3	3	18.628	5.131
have	20	14	12	18.010	1.953
couldn't	21	3	3	13.695	4.324
played	22	5	5	13.559	3.113
finished	23	3	2	12.680	4.131

Table A8: Losers Corpus 'you' collocates

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
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know	1	120	39	768.926	5.230
're	2	28	16	98.077	3.671
've	3	27	17	65.869	2.901
can	4	13	8	34.233	3.069
alright	5	6	5	25.255	4.171
laughed	6	3	1	24.591	5.908
regretted	7	3	1	24.591	5.908
look	8	7	7	20.429	3.289
don't	9	11	6	19.646	2.401
to	10	1	1	12.214	-3.198

Table A9: *Losers Corpus 'they' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	30	20	154.498	4.831
've	2	22	14	75.457	3.667
were	3	14	11	63.421	4.472
are	4	9	7	31.095	3.729
'll	5	7	5	29.889	4.317
should	6	6	5	24.554	4.196
weren't	7	4	3	22.817	5.268
could	8	5	4	20.191	4.161
chose	9	2	1	19.341	6.969
gambled	10	2	1	19.341	6.969
seemed	11	2	1	13.828	5.969
haven't	12	3	3	13.044	4.384
didn't	13	4	4	12.544	3.509
had	14	5	3	12.311	2.987
don't	15	6	5	11.855	2.588

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